

THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS REINFORCED WITH GLASSY MICRO BALLOONS

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1 Introduction

In developing the high speed robotics hand system, a newly designed structure component must be needed with excellent features, i.e., low density (less than 0.5g/cm³), high stiffness and high strength. In order to satisfy both of low density and high stiffness/ strength, a composite material system, which will consist of core material with low density [1] and outer fibrous material of woven type or knitted type, is one of the candidates for various application.

In this study, thermal conductivity of newly developed core material of composite materials system with low density is investigated. By using an analytical model of micro porous materials, a homogenization theory with multi-scale analytical method will be described in order to evaluate the thermal conductivity of the composite.

2 Fabrication method of the composite

2.1 Materials used

The “Sirasu Balloon (SB)” *Maarlite 723C* of Marunaka-Hakudo Co. was used for reinforcements. Sirasu Balloon has micro glassy spherical hollow shell body which was manufactured from volcanic glassy “*pumice tuff*” by heating rapidly at about 1300K. Therefore, it has superior heat resistance, strong impact resistance, and high thermal insulation, for this reason, it could be applied to exterior wall and so on. From the reference of *Maarlite 723C*, the bulk density is 0.15±0.025g/cm², the average diameter is 40-50 μm, float ratio 70-80 wt%, and Ph 6.0-7.0.

The epoxy resin used was Ciba-Geigy *GY-250*. The resin is unplasticized diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) with mean molecular weight of 380 and an epoxide equivalent of 180 - 190g/eq. From technical data for the matrix resin, bending strength σ_b is 55MPa, tensile strength σ_t is 62MPa, glass transition temperature $\tan \delta_{dry}$; 428K, fracture toughness G_{IC} ; 0.15kJ/m² and water absorption ratio is 0.16%. The hexa-hydrophthalic anhydride hardener HN-5500 of Hitachi Chemical Co., Ltd. and the accelerator #2E4MZ of Shikoku Chemical Co. were also used for mixture.

2.2 Developed fabrication method

The Sirasu Balloon/Epoxy composites (SB/E composites) was fabricated in batches by mixing 186g of Epoxy resin and 200ml of *Maarlite 723C*. In developed mold process, in order to prevent the entrapment of air bubbles, we take the degas process for the mixture by holding it in a vacuum chamber before curing. And the mixture was kept in a furnace by following the original heat cycle. A fabricated composite are shown in Fig.1. Observing to Fig.1, the composite is separated into three layers. Top layer consists of SBs and epoxy resin. Middle layer is filled with resin, and the bottom layer has broken SBs and resin.

The analysis of digital image processing was performed. Fig.2 shows the result of stochastic analysis for mean diameter of balloon particles against the depth along thickness direction in micro porous composites. We observed a characteristic curve for balloon diameter due to the buoyancy of balloons in matrix resin. In the upper position near the surface of fabricated materials, relatively large size of balloons were observed and mean diameter

Table 1 Mechanical property of SB Composites and Epoxy Resin.

	Upper	SB composites Middle	Lower	Epoxy resin
Density (10^3kg/m^3)	0.626	0.630	0.814	1.20
Bending modulus (GPa)	2.97	3.14	4.46	3.29
Bending strength (MPa)	22.6	28.3	44.2	54.5
Specific bending modulus(GPa)	4.74	4.98	5.48	2.74
Specific bending strength(MPa)	36.1	44.9	54.3	45.4

Fig.1. Photograph of SB/Epoxy composites fabricated by developed method.

Fig.3. SEM photograph of the composites in Upper position.

Fig.2. Mean diameter of Sirasu Balloons against depth along thickness direction.

Fig.4. Stress-strain curve of the composite.

takes larger value of $51\mu\text{m}$. Therefore, the density of composites could be small and specific bending modulus and bending strength take lower values than that of specimens from middle or lower position.

2.3 Specimens and experiments

For the experiment, the composites in upper layer of SB and resin part were machined into the precise shape of specimens of coupon type. The specimen classified into three types (Upper/Middle/Lower) by its position in top layer.

The density of upper layer specimen is 0.626, the middle one is 0.630 and the lower is 0.814. According to SEM photograph of composites in Upper position (Fig.3), we can not observe any large size void in composites after improvement. Large size glass balloons are easily observed in Upper position rather than in Lower one.

Bending tests were performed under the conditions of 50%RH at 298K. The cross head speed (C.H.S.) was kept at 0.1mm/min and the span 64mm. The load and strain were recorded by personal computer throughout the tests.

From the experimental results, mechanical behavior and properties of composites were examined. Fig. 4 shows the Stress σ – Strain ϵ curves of bending test. The stress - strain curves of specimen indicate linear behavior through all stages from earlier stage of loading to the maximum. For upper layer specimen at 298K and 50%RH, specific bending modulus (bending modulus/density) is 4.74GPa and specific bending strength (bending strength/density) is 36.1MPa. For middle, specific bending modulus 4.98GPa and specific bending strength 44.9MPa. For lower one, specific bending modulus 5.48GPa and specific bending strength 54.3MPa. The mechanical properties of micro porous composites at three different positions are summarized in Table 1.

3 Theoretical analysis of the Composites

3.1 A Model for FEM Analysis

The effects of material properties and configurations on the thermal properties of the composite are discussed from the viewpoint of micromechanical study. Making a dispersion model of micro porous materials microscopically, we apply a homogenization theory with multi-scale analytical method [2] for evaluation of the thermal behavior of the composite system.

It is easily found from Fig. 3 that the balloons were dispersed well over the observed area and few air bubbles were observed in the figure. Therefore, the microscopic structure of the composites could assume to be periodical for the analysis. We introduce a simple two- and three- dimensional dispersion model for evaluation of the macroscopic mechanical behavior of the composites.

Fig. 5 shows a two-dimensional unit cell model for FEM analysis of thermal conduction, which consists of a cylindrical hollow shell in the center of cell and the epoxy resin of remaining part. The white part of circle shows the air in the Sirasu Balloon. We assume that micro cylindrical hollow shells are perfectly bonded to the matrix, and the air of 1013 hPa (1 atm) is filled inside the balloon. And the diameter of cylindrical hollow shells is set to 40 μ m from the mean value of SB and the distance between the two balloons were determined by the volume fraction of the composites used in the experiments. The unit cell model is divided into

quadrangle elements for FEM analysis. The total number of node is 2103 and the total number of quadrangle element is 2022.

3.2 Thermal conductivity of the composite

Some numerical calculations were performed by using a model of micro porous materials and setting thermal properties of each material at the temperature. The SB was assumed to take constant elastic property independent of temperature.

Stress distribution obtained from the 3D analytical model shows that the stresses in the membrane of balloon is higher than that in the matrix. Though the thickness and diameter of balloons are small, the micro balloons could play an important role as reinforcements of the composites. The analytical results for the tension test at 298K made a good agreement with experimental ones. It can be said that a unit cell model of micro porous materials is valid for evaluation of the mechanical behavior of the composite system in temperature conditions [3].

Table 2 Thermal properties of composites for analysis.

	Air	SB	Epoxy
Thermal Conductivity(W/mK)	0.035	1.27	0.2
Specific Heat(J/kgK)	1012	1000	1000
Density(kg/m3)	0.9	2800	1180

Fig.5. FEM model of composites for thermal analysis.

Fig.6. Relationship between thermal conductivity and volume fraction.

Employing our dispersion model for heat flow problem, FEM analysis was performed for the evaluation of thermal conductivity at the volume fraction of 0.1 - 0.7. The thermal properties used in the analysis are shown in Table 2. Sirasu Balloons mainly consist of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 , and have some small portions of oxides. Their conductivity has NOT been measured yet. Therefore we estimate the thermal conductivity λ_T for FEM analysis by using the following equation;

$$\lambda_T = \sum \omega_i \cdot a_i \quad (1)$$

where ω indicates the weight percent of ingredient and a is the value of thermal conductivity. The value of λ_T is found to be 1.27 W/mK.

Fig. 6 shows Relationship between thermal conductivity and volume fraction. The values for the estimation by Maxwell's theory and Russel's theory are also plotted in the same figure. The thermal conductivity of Sirasu Balloon is higher than that of epoxy resin. Viewing this figure, the thermal conductivity of developed composites, which is marked with solid circles, gradually decreases as the volume fraction of composites increases. The result of FEM analysis takes lower values than that of Russell's and the Maxwell's theory is not valid for estimation. It is found that

the air which Sirasu Balloons and/or the composites contain affects on thermal conductivity. When the balloons gather and touch with each other, the thermal conductivity of the composites may become higher. A percolation model would be required to evaluate actual thermal conductivity.

4 Conclusion

We developed the micro porous composites reinforced with glassy micro balloons for advanced mechanical system. The thermal conductivity of composites was analyzed by using a unit model of micro porous materials.

- (1) The composites fabricated by improved method have excellent properties, i.e. higher value in bending strength and bending modulus, and did not contain any large size void of air.
- (2) It is found to be that a unit cell model of micro porous materials is valid for evaluation of the mechanical behavior of the composite system.
- (3) The thermal conductivity of developed composites gradually decreases as the volume fraction of composites increases.

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